

ENES Pilot Node

European Network for Earth System Modeling.
Advancing Interoperability in Climate Science and Beyond.

FACTSHEET FOR:

Scientists; Research groups, Communities, and Organisations;
Research Infrastructures; Education and Training Institutions, Learners

Pilot Node Profile

The ENES Pilot Node integrates ENES services with the next generation of EOSC Core capabilities to deliver an interoperable and scalable environment that enables AI-driven analysis, big data processing, and provenance tracking, fostering seamless access, innovation, and federation across scientific research domains.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Enable federated login for accessing Node's exchange services {production}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **ENESLab**
(Compute, Storage, Data Analytics, Management, and Visualisation)
- **Provenance Service**
(Data Reproducibility, Data Management)
- **Provenance Explorer**
(Data Management, Data Exploration)
- **ENES Thematic Data Catalogue**
(Data Discovery)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

1. Perform interactive analysis and visualisation on scientific data

As a scientist, I want to get access to computing resources so that I can run interactive analysis, AI/ML-based applications, and visualisation on scientific data.

Persona: Scientist

Objective: Get access to computing resources for running data analysis.

Before: The scientist needed to collect and download data from multiple sources, set up the environment, and prepare homemade scripts to run the analysis, which was usually carried out under strict constraints in terms of computational and storage resources.

After: The scientist gets access to an open and fully-configured data science environment, including data, computational resources, and a feature-rich software stack that enables interactive analytics, big data processing, and data visualisation.

2. Manage provenance information associated with scientific workflows

As a scientist, I want to run my analytics workflow and publish and/or manage provenance information at different levels of granularity.

Persona: Scientist

Objective: Track and manage provenance metadata in complex scientific workflows.

Before: Scientists could not easily reconstruct how a particular result was obtained, which data was used, and which steps and parameters was applied in the workflow, thus making computational science much less transparent and repeatable.

After: The scientist has clear and structured information about the origin and transformation of data. This makes it possible to reproduce and validate results with confidence, identify and correct errors more efficiently, share and reuse data and workflows across the community, and increase transparency and trust in scientific research.

ENES Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- AAI
- Service Catalogue
- Discovery Hub
- Helpdesk
- Monitoring
- Deployment Service

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- Cloud Compute
- Storage

Value of the Node piloting activities

The piloting activity is delivering new capabilities in EOSC for the climate change community. For instance the yProv service fills an existing gap in the current service community offering with respect to provenance management. Such a service allows researchers to store, access, visualize, and share provenance documents with other scientists. It's worthwhile mentioning that due to its domain-agnostic design and interoperable interface such a service can be reused by any other research

community in EOSC. Moreover, the ENES thematic data catalog based on the STAC specifications contributes to the integration of the ENES resources into the broader EOSC ecosystem, supporting their connection with the EOSC Knowledge Graph and other EOSC services. By adopting open standards and interoperable metadata, the catalog enables climate researchers to expose and share rich, discoverable information that can be seamlessly linked within the EOSC framework.

Next steps

Future activities will focus on reinforcing the ENES user stories to implement a comprehensive user journey and strengthen the integration with the EOSC Core services, as well as the link with the other pilot Nodes.

These will be complemented by testing and validation efforts to consolidate the ENES node capabilities and to ensure a more efficient and seamless experience for researchers.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

ENES Pilot Node:

www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/enes

ENESLab:

<https://ds.eneslab.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu/>

ENES Data Catalogue:

<https://catalogue.eneslab.pilot.eosc-beyond.eu/>

Provenance Service:

<http://yprov.disi.unitn.it:3000/>

